

AN ONLINE IMAGE COMPRESSION ALGORITHM USING SINGULAR VALUE DECOMPOSITION AND ADAPTIVE VECTOR QUANTIZATION *

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ABSTRACT

In this paper we propose novel strategies for reducing the practical limitations of the Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) for image compression. First, the computational cost is reduced by computing only a limited number of eigenvectors. Second, an online Adaptive Vector Quantization (AVQ) method is used to achieve a low bit rate. Simulation results show that the proposed algorithm is better than the discrete cosine transform (DCT) and previous hybrid VQ-SVD in terms of distortion, bit rate, and image quality.

Index Terms: Image coding, singular value decomposition, vector quantization

1 Introduction

In recent years several image compression algorithms based on transform coding have been proposed (see [1] and references therein). In transform coding, the source image is decomposed into a set of coefficients (or frequency components) by using a linear transform, and then these coefficients are subsequently quantized and coded. For instance, the use of the SVD in transform coding consists of computing the eigenvalues and the eigenvectors of each block in the image and then transmitting both the eigenvectors and the eigenvalues to the decoder.

The SVD is a powerful transform for image compression because it provides optimal energy compaction but, unfortunately, its usefulness for real applications is severely limited because both the computational and the transmission cost - since both the eigenvalues and eigenvectors must be transmitted - are quite high [4]. In order to mitigate these limitations, in this paper we propose a new algorithm, called Adaptive Singular Value Decomposition (ASVD), which computes and transmits a reduced set of eigenvectors. In ASVD - as in other SVD-based algorithms [3, 6] - the eigenvectors are coded using VQ [2]. However, the ASVD differs from previous work in that the eigenvectors's codebooks (which are

initially empty) are generated for each image by potentially sending eigenvectors generated from the current block. As a consequence, a suitable set of initial codebooks need not be generated *a priori* and the codebooks are dynamically adapted to changes in the eigenvectors.

This paper is structured as follows. In Section 2 we propose the new image compression algorithm. Section 3 shows computer simulation results. Finally, Section 4 is devoted to conclusions.

2 The ASVD Algorithm

In this Section we present the encoding and the decoding functions performed in ASVD.

2.1 Encoder

The first step in ASVD is to partition the image in blocks of dimension $n \times n$. Then, the blocks are processed independently as follows:

The eigenvalues, $\lambda(j)$, $j = 1, \dots, n$ ($\lambda(j) \geq \lambda(j+1)$), of the matrix $\mathbf{R}_x = \mathbf{X}^T \mathbf{X}$ are calculated and then the number, p , of eigenvectors that must be computed is determined as the smallest value that satisfies the expression:

$$\sum_{j=1}^p \lambda(j) \geq \beta \sum_{j=1}^n \lambda(j), \quad p = 1, \dots, n \quad (1)$$

where β is a real-valued parameter. In the next step, the eigenvectors $\mathbf{u}_R(j)$, $j = 1, \dots, p$ are computed by solving the problem:

$$(\mathbf{R}_x - \lambda(j)\mathbf{I})\mathbf{u}_R(j) = \mathbf{0}, \quad j = 1, \dots, p \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{I}$ and $\mathbf{0}$ are the $n \times n$ identity and $n \times n$ zero matrices, respectively. The eigenvectors $\mathbf{u}_L(j)$, $j = 1, \dots, p$ are calculated as follows:

$$\mathbf{u}_L(j) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\lambda(j)}} \mathbf{X} \mathbf{u}_R(j), \quad j = 1, \dots, p \quad (3)$$

It is interesting to note that expression (1) has multiple objectives. The first objective is to reduce the computational cost associated with the SVD transform

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by computing fewer eigenvectors. The second objective is to determine the number of eigenvalues needed to achieve a fixed percentage of the maximum energy of each block. Note that only p eigenvalues and $2p$ eigenvectors must be coded and transmitted. The eigenvalues, $\sqrt{\lambda(j)}$, $j = 1, \dots, p$, are uniformly quantized and coded using fixed-length codes. The eigenvectors are coded using an Online Adaptive Vector Quantization (OAVQ) technique. More specifically, for the j -th eigenvectors, $\mathbf{u}_R(j)$ and $\mathbf{u}_L(j)$, the OAVQ technique selects the codeword in the codebook $\mathbf{E}_j$ (initially empty), $\mathbf{e}_j^*$, that minimizes the Euclidean distance, $\mathcal{D}(\cdot, \cdot)$, i.e.,

$$\mathbf{e}_j^* = \arg \min_{\mathbf{e}_j \in \mathbf{E}_j} \mathcal{D}(\mathbf{u}(j), \mathbf{e}_j) \quad (4)$$

where $\mathbf{u}(j)$ denotes the current eigenvector. The encoder transmits the index of $\mathbf{e}_j^*$ only when the Euclidean distance is less than a parameter γ_j . Otherwise, new codewords are uniformly quantized and coded, and the current eigenvector is inserted into the local codebook by replacing the Least Frequently Used (LFU) codeword when the codebook size, σ , is exceeded. For each eigenvector, $\mathbf{u}_R(j)$ and $\mathbf{u}_L(j)$, a flag (f_R and f_L) indicates whether a codebook index or a new codeword is transmitted. Recall that the number of eigenvalues, p , depends on the source block and p is not known to the decoder. For this reason, when each eigenvalue and the corresponding eigenvectors are transmitted, the encoder transmits a flag f_c indicating whether another eigenvalue will be sent or another block will be processed.

2.2 Decoder

The decoder simply interprets the transmitted information and evaluates the following expression:

$$\hat{\mathbf{X}} = \sum_{j=1}^p \sqrt{\hat{\lambda}(j)} \hat{\mathbf{u}}_L(j) \hat{\mathbf{u}}_R^T(j) \quad (5)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{X}}$ is the $n \times n$ recovered block, p is the number of transmitted eigenvalues, $\sqrt{\hat{\lambda}(j)}$ is the decoded eigenvalue, and $\hat{\mathbf{u}}_L(j)$ and $\hat{\mathbf{u}}_R(j)$ are the decoded eigenvectors. The eigenvectors are obtained in two different ways, depending on the transmitted data. The first is to look for the codeword corresponding to the transmitted index in the local codebook $\mathbf{D}_j$ (which is initially empty). Alternatively, when the encoder transmits a new codeword, the codeword is decoded and it is inserted into the local codebook by replacing the LFU codeword when the codebook size, σ , is exceeded.

2.3 Bit Rate

The bit rate of the ASVD algorithm for an $N \times N$ image can be computed as follows:

$$\mathcal{R}_{ASVD} = (\mathcal{B}_\lambda + \mathcal{B}_{\mathbf{u}_R} + \mathcal{B}_{\mathbf{u}_L} + \mathcal{B}_f) / N^2 \quad (6)$$

where $\mathcal{B}_\lambda$ is the number of bits used to quantize the eigenvalues:

$$\mathcal{B}_\lambda = \sum_{i=1}^n n_{\lambda(i)} \times bit_\lambda$$

where n is the block size. That is, we multiply the number of i -th eigenvalues transmitted for all blocks, $n_{\lambda(i)}$, by the number of bits used to quantize each eigenvalue, bit_λ . The second term in (6) refers to the number of bits used to specify the eigenvectors, $\mathbf{u}_R$, to the decoder. The second term in (6) can be calculated by:

$$\mathcal{B}_{\mathbf{u}_R} = \sum_{i=1}^n (n_{\mathbf{u}_R(i)} \times bit_{\mathbf{u}_R} + (n_{\lambda(i)} - n_{\mathbf{u}_R(i)}) \times \log_2(\sigma))$$

In the expression above we can distinguish two parts. The first term is the number of bits used to send new codewords, i.e., the number of codewords transmitted, $n_{\mathbf{u}_R(i)}$, multiplied by the number of bits used to encode the new codewords, $bit_{\mathbf{u}_R}$. The second term in (7) corresponds to the number of bits used to code the indices. Here, the parameter σ is the codebook size. A similar definition is used for the third term in (6):

$$\mathcal{B}_{\mathbf{u}_L} = \sum_{i=1}^n (n_{\mathbf{u}_L(i)} \times bit_{\mathbf{u}_L} + (n_{\lambda(i)} - n_{\mathbf{u}_L(i)}) \times \log_2(\sigma))$$

Finally, the fourth term in (6) represents the bits used in sending the flags f_R , f_L and f_c . We assume that the decoder knows the size, n , of the block $\mathbf{X}$ and thus the flag f_c is not transmitted for the n -th eigenvalue. The term $\mathcal{B}_f$ is therefore given by:

$$\mathcal{B}_f = \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} 3 \times n_{\lambda(i)} + 2 \times n_{\lambda(n)}$$

3 Simulation Results

In this section the results of several computer simulations are presented to illustrate the performance of the ASVD algorithm and to establish a comparison with the DCT and the algorithm proposed in by Yang and Lu which combines non-adaptive VQ and the SVD [6]. The 512×512 8-bits monochrome image in Figure 1 has been considered. This image has been divided into 4×4 blocks. The transform coefficients obtained with the DCT, the ASVD, and the Yang-Lu algorithm have been uniformly quantized and coded using a fixed-length code of 7 bits.

In the ASVD algorithm, the parameter β has been chosen in order to retain the 99% of the maximum energy of each block, i.e., $\beta = 0.99$. Each component of the new codewords are uniformly quantized and coded using 5 bits. The eigenvector codebooks are initially empty and their maximum size is $\sigma = 32$. The remaining ASVD parameters are: $\gamma_2 = \gamma_3 = \gamma_4 = 0.5$ and γ_1 takes

Figure 1: Image used in the simulations

different values ($\gamma_1 = 0.1, 0.01, 0.001$ and 0.0001). For comparison, the number of coefficients per block used with the DCT are $n_c = 4, 5, 6$ and 7 . In the Yang-Lu algorithm, only two eigenvalues are coded. Also, the initial codebooks used for this algorithm contain 32 codewords and they have been generated using four 512×512 images and the Linde-Buzo-Gray (LBG) algorithm. The algorithm performance has been measured in terms of the distortion as a function of bit rate (bits per pixel). The distortion has been calculated as the peak signal to noise ratio: $PSNR = 10 \log_{10}(255^2/MSE)$ dB where MSE is the mean square error between the original and the recovered image.

Figure 3 shows a comparison of the three algorithm in terms of bit rate-distortion. It is apparent that the proposed algorithm yields better results than the another two algorithms. In addition, from expression (6), we can obtain the minimum and maximum bit-rate of the ASVD algorithm: $\mathcal{R}_{ASVDmin} = 1.25$ bits/pixel and $\mathcal{R}_{ASVDmax} = 12.4375$ bits/pixel. Note that the values in Figure 3 for the ASVD algorithm are close to the minimum value. We note also that we have used a simple method to quantize both the eigenvalues and the eigenvectors, and other techniques in the literature might be used in order to further improve the performance of the algorithm. For instance, Figure 3 shows the performance of ASVD when entropy codes are used in coding the codebooks indices and the new codewords.

In Figure 2 we can see the image obtained with ASVD at a rate of 2.2269 bpp and PSNR of 31.41 dB, with DCT at a rate of 2.1875 bpp and PSNR of 25.42 dB, and with Yang-Lu algorithm at a rate of 2.1250 and PSNR of 29.47 dB. Note that ASVD and the Yang-Lu algorithm provide better image quality than the DCT, especially in the high frequency regions of the image (see the seat-back and cloth).

We have not determined the analytical expression of

Figure 2: Recovered imaged using: (a) ASVD at a rate of 2.2269 bpp; (b) Yang-Lu algorithm at a rate of 2.1250 bpp; (c) DCT at a rate of 2.1875 bpp.

Figure 3: Comparison among ASVD, DCT and Yang-Lu algorithm.

Figure 4: Comparison of ASVD and DCT in terms of floating point operations: (a) Encoder complexity; (b) Decoder complexity

γ_1	0.1	0.01	0.001	0.0001
New codewords	0.1%	3.2%	20.5%	39.5%

Table 1: Percentage of new codewords

the ASVD complexity but empirical results show that the computational cost is acceptable. For instance, Figure 4 shows the number of floating point operations (flops) performed in both the ASVD and DCT encoders for the simulation show in Figure 3. It can be seen that the ASVD encoder is about 7 times more computational expensive than the DCT. However, Figure 4 (b) shows that the ASVD decoder process requires less floating operations than the DCT. The explanation for this disparity is that the number of transmitted eigenvalues is less than the non-zero coefficients used to recover the image using the DCT and, therefore, the expression (5) uses a reduced number of operations. We also have observed that for this simulation only 34% of eigenvectors have been calculated. Table 1 shows that the percentage of these eigenvectors that have been coded.

4 Conclusions

This paper considers image compression using Singular Value Decomposition. New strategies have been proposed which reduce the practical limitations of this optimal transform. First, the computational complexity is reduced by calculating relatively few eigenvectors. The number of eigenvectors that must be retained in the encoder is determined considering the energy of the source image. Second, the bit rate is improved by using AVQ to quantize the transmitted eigenvectors. Our results show that this technique has better performance than the DCT at a modest increase in computational cost.

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